

ON RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN VISCOSITY AND SURFACE TENSION OF LIQUIDS.

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A number of equations connecting viscosity and surface tension, obtained by combining (a) equations connecting viscosity and density with or without temperature on one hand and (b) Macleod's equation connecting surface tension and density on the other, has been examined. The simplest and one of the most successful equation is found to have the form, $\log \log \eta = m\gamma^{\frac{1}{2}} + c$.

Buehler (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, 42, 1207) has combined Mott Sauer's equation (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 88, 154) $\log \log \eta = md - 2.9$ with Sugden's well-known parachor equation (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1177);

$$P = \frac{M}{d} \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

In Mott Sauer's equation viscosity is to be taken in centipoises, m is a constant characteristic of each liquid and further mM which is denoted by I is an additive function. Hence the equation obtained by Buehler is

$$\log \log \eta = \frac{I}{P} \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}} - 2.9.$$

Buehler shows the value of I/P should on the average, be 1.2. Therefore his equation assumes the form $\log \log \eta = 1.2 \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}} - 2.9$. He claims that this equation connecting viscosity and surface tension is better than the one advanced by Silvermann and Roseveare (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4460) : $\eta^{-1} = k\gamma^{-\frac{1}{2}} + c$. His claim does not seem to be justified as Table I will show. Associated liquids are not included in this table because Buehler does not claim that his equation could be applied to them.

TABLE I.

Liquid.	Temp. range.	γ range γ max.- γ min.	Constants of Silvermann and Roseveare's equation.		Silvermann and Roseveare's eq.	Maximum % diff. Buehler's equation.
			$K \times 10^{-3}$.	$C \times 10^{-3}$.		
CCl_4	20-170°	17.15	3.500	-1.400	5.0	33.2
Chlorobenzene	20-160	15.76	4.180	-1.610	3.2	11.0
Toluene ...	0-110	12.15	4.930	-1.966	3.9	4.7
Acetone ...	-71-56	16.20	5.170	-2.052	3.0	4.5
Benzene ..	0-100	13.85	4.465	-1.772	7.4	12.15
Ether ...	-95-0	12.78	4.770	-1.942	1.3	18.6
<i>p</i> -Xylene	10-130	13.00	4.500	-1.773	2.1	3.1

TABLE II.

Liquid.	Temp. range.	Constants.						
		Silvermann and Roseveare's equations.		Buehler's modified equation.		Maximum % difference		
		$K \times 10^{-1}$.	$C \times 10^{-1}$.	w .	C .	Buehler's modified equation.	Silvermann and Roseveare's equation.	Buehler's original equation.
Butyric acid	0-130°	3'24	-1'326	1'03	-2'326	1'95	5'2	51'3
n-Propyl alcohol	0-90	3'75	-1'658	1'89	-4'020	1'0	4'9	28'6
Ethyl acetate	0-70	4'20	-1'693	1'28	-2'767	1'23	1'3	15'7
Ethylene chloride	0-80	3'31	-1'279	0'95	-1'280	1'0	6'4	11'1
Chloroform	0-60	3'22	-1'238	0'86	-2'078	1'6	2'0	15'3
Chlorobenzene	20-160	4'18	-1'610	1'00	-2'464	1'7	3'2	1'0
Carbon tetrachloride	20-170	3'30	-1'400	0'87	-1'996	2'0	5'0	63'2
Toluene	0-110	4'93	-1'966	1'13	-2'730	1'3	3'5	4'7
Acetone	-87-56	5'17	-2'052	1'30	-3'140	1'9	3'0	4'5
Methyl alcohol	-87-0	2'54	-1'045	1'70	-3'814	1'1	6'2	46'2
Ether	-95-0	4'77	-1'942	1'36	-3'180	2'0	1'5	18'6
Bromobenzene	60-143	3'34	-1'264	0'75	-1'860	1'0	4'0	9'7
Ethylformate	0-50	4'85	-1'955	1'24	-2'962	0'7	1'0	6'8
isoButyl bromide	0-90	3'64	-1'469	1'00	-2'337	1'4	2'1	27'2
Methyl isobutyrate	0-90	4'87	-2'027	1'34	-3'082	2'0	2'4	22'6
o-Nitrotoluene	0-100	3'88	-1'492	1'61	-3'937	1'2	0'7	4'5
Ethyl iodide	0-70	4'00	-1'572	0'94	-2'265	0'5	2'9	9'2
Methyl ethyl ketone	0-80	4'77	-1'930	1'22	-2'895	1'1	0'9	9'0
m-Toluidine	0-60	4'40	-1'744	2'50	-6'010	0'9	1'7	24'2
Octane	0-80	3'85	-1'602	1'12	-2'552	0'6	0'7	7'0
m-Xylene	0-130	4'30	-1'694	1'18	-2'540	1'1	4'0	8'8
Nitrobenzene	5-80	4'76	-1'810	1'72	-4'285	0'7	1'0	12'0
Propyl acetate	0-100	4'00	-1'639	1'20	-2'760	1'2	1'2	27'0
Ethyl alcohol	-98-70	2'98	-1'285	1'50	-3'200	2'2	15'9	72'5
Acetic acid	20-110	3'34	-1'375	1'03	-2'336	0'9	1'0	37'8

The original Buehler's equation has general constants as will be evident from the equation itself.

TABLE III.

Temp.	γ obs.	γ Calc.		% Difference		
		Buehler's equation.	Buehler's modified equation.	Buehler's equation	Buehler's modified equation.	
Propionic acid : ($m=0.955$; $C=-2.16$).						
0°	28.80	37.64	29.20	30.4	1.39	
10	27.50	36.28	28.03	31.9	1.92	
20	26.50	34.93	26.94	31.8	1.66	
30	25.60	33.73	25.76	31.7	0.62	
40	24.60	32.56	24.59	32.4	-0.04	
50	23.65	31.49	23.50	33.0	-0.60	
60	22.60	30.45	22.48	34.7	-0.53	
70	21.70	29.38	21.40	35.4	-1.38	
80	20.70	28.39	20.41	37.2	-1.40	
90	19.80	27.39	19.45	38.4	-1.76	
100	18.75	26.41	18.52	40.5	-1.22	
110	17.80	25.45	17.60	43.0	-1.12	
120	16.80	24.50	16.71	45.7	-0.53	
130	15.80	23.55	15.83	49.0	0.19	
140	14.90	22.55	14.82	51.4	-0.53	
Benzene : ($m=1.22$; $C=-2.9167$).						
0	31.87	33.24	31.87	4.30	0.0	
10	30.19	31.89	30.19	5.63	0.0	
20	28.88	30.20	28.88	4.57	0.0	
30	27.58	28.67	27.56	3.96	-0.07	
40	26.28	27.30	26.24	3.89	-0.15	
50	25.09	26.83	25.02	6.93	-0.30	
60	23.82	24.82	23.81	4.22	-0.04	
70	22.55	23.60	22.57	4.67	-0.09	
80	20.28	22.75	20.36	12.15	0.39	
*100	18.02	19.57	18.13	8.60	0.61	

* This temperature is above B. P.

If the assumption that $I/P = 1.2$ is done away with and Buehler's equation is written in the form $\log \log \eta = m\gamma^{\frac{1}{2}} + c$ (which will henceforward be referred to as Buehler's modified equation) it is found that the equation gives very satisfactory results, and surprisingly enough, by some compensation of errors, the equation is found to apply satisfactorily not only to simple but also to associated liquids, not only to ordinary temperatures but also to temperatures above the boiling point of liquids.

Table II gives a comparison of the three equations.

In order to show the extent to which the Buehler's modified equation agrees with actual measurements, the results for propionic acid, an associated liquid, and for benzene, a simple liquid, are given in detail in Table III.

A number of other equations connecting viscosity with density with or without temperature can be combined with Sugden's parachor equation and the equations so obtained giving relationships between viscosity and surface tension are found, on examination, to be quite accurate though none of them is as simple as the modified Buehler's equation.

The data have been taken from Landolt Bornstein Tabellen (1923¹ edition) and Tables Annuelles (Vol. V, 1937).

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